

2024	Fauna Balkana University of Novi Sad, Serbia	Volume 5 pp 80–88
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Endogean and cavernicolous Coleoptera of the Balkans. XXV. A new species of *Mayetia* Mulsant et Rey, 1875 (Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae) from North Macedonia

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SUMMARY. The new species of *Mayetia macedonica* sp. n. is described from Skopska Crna Gora Mt. in North Macedonia. Data on all available faunistic records for all Balkanic *Mayetia* species are given.

KEY WORDS: Balkans, Euplectitae, Mayetiini, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

Mayetiini Scheerpeltz, 1925 is a small tribe of minute endogean Euplectitae which currently comprises only three genera, *Mayetia* Mulsant et Rey, 1875 with 174 species names (Hlaváč pers. database) distributed mainly in the Mediterranean region but known also from USA (18 species), Neotropical region (3), Gabon (1), Nepal (1) and Japan (1). Two Afrotropical genera, monospecific *Typhloleptodes* Jeannel, 1953 is known from The Democratic Republic of Congo and *Typhlodes* Jeannel, 1951 with 12 species names known from The Democratic Republic of Congo (7) and Gabon (5).

Mayetia is one of largest known genera of the Pselaphinae and their species belong between smallest representants of the whole Coleoptera. The species of *Mayetia* are minute, narrow, elongate filiform anophthalmous beetles with the length of 0.7–1.3 mm (Orousset 2022) and they are characterised by dentate labrum with median notch; antennae with 11 antennomeres, antennal club composed with 2

fused antennomeres, terminal antennomere with six large spatulate setae, sometimes transparent and almost invisible; maxillary palpi in the rest position are located in lateral palpaire fovea; posterior coxae contiguous; genital segment IX of male complete; tarsi composed of two tarsomeres, first short, second long with one claw, lacking paronguel setae and aedeagus lacking basal capsule.

Although very small body size, *Mayetia* is one of best studied genera of Pselaphinae. The tribe was transferred to the Pselaphinae (Pselaphidae at that time) by Jeannel and Coiffait (1955), the same year when also the revision of the genus *Mayetia* was published (Coiffait 1955). In total 45 species were treated in the revision. Since this work many species have been synonymized and many new described. All our knowledge has been summarized by Jean Orousset (2022) in his excellent commented world catalogue of the genus.

The aim of this paper is the description of fourth species of *Mayetia* from the Balkan peninsula from North Macedonia.

The material used for this study was collected under research permit granted to the junior author by the “Ministerstvo za životna sredina i prostorno planiranje” (UP1-11/1-546/2023) of the Republic of North Macedonia.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Specimen handling, imaging and measurements. Body or body parts were embedded in a water-soluble medium (polyvinylpyrrolidone). Embedded specimens were examined with a Leica S8APO stereo-microscope with diffuse lighting at magnifications up to 128 ×. Images were made using a Canon EOS 700D camera mounted on a Motic BA 410E-T compound microscope in transmitted or diffused reflected light. Resulting images were focus stacked using Zerene Stacker and then postprocessed in Paint.Net, Paint, XnView and Live Photo Galery. Line drawing was made using a drawing tube attached to a Zeiss microscope. Plates were arranged in Paint and Paint.Net.

Head capsule length was measured from the anteriormost point of frons to the posterior margin of lateral corners of head capsule; the elytral length was measured along the suture; the width is maximum width across a given structure. Lengths of abdominal segments were measured along midline. Body length is a combined length of the head, pronotum, elytra and abdomen.

Morphological terms generally follow Chandler (2001), with modifications that update terminology in agreement with that currently broadly accepted for Coleoptera. Label data off the holotype and paratypes are quoted verbatim, with slashes (/) separating lines on the label. All type specimens were provided with the following red printed label: HOLOTYPE or PARATYPE, *Mayetia macedonica* sp. n., Hlaváč & Janák det., 2022.

TAXONOMY

Mayetia macedonica sp. n. Figs 1–16

MATERIAL EXAMINED: Holotype, ♂: NORTH MACEDONIA, with two labels “North Macedonia, 15.5.2023. Skopska Crna Gora Mt., Brodec env., 900 m,” [white, printed], “42.14121N, 21.44026E, J. Janák lgt., soil washing” [white, printed], (PCPH). Paratypes, 3♀♀: same data as for holotype (PCPH).

DIAGNOSIS. Eyes completely atrophied; labrum in male with three, in female with two pairs of spiny protuberances; left mandible with a single tooth, right with bifid tooth; maxillary palpi with all palpomeres lacking sensory processes; antennae about 0.2 mm long, antennal club dimerous, scape about as long as wide and about 1.55 times as long as globular pedicel, antennomeres 3–8 transversal, 5 about 1.8 times as wide as long, 7 twice as wide as long, terminal antenomere with dense setae, flattened sensilla on antenomere 11 invisible; pronotum inversely trapezoidal; elytra longer than wide, lacking basal foveae, carinae or striae; legs with metatrochanter simple, lacking spur.

DESCRIPTION. Body length 1.00–1.05 mm (Figs 1, 2), maximal width in midlength of head, about 0.12–0.13 mm.

Head (Figs 3, 4) about 1.02–1.03 times as wide as long, about 1.1 as wide as pronotum, widest in posterior third, from here convergent posteriad and anteriad; basal capsule separated from neck region by occipital constriction, neck region retracted into pronotum, posterior margin of basal capsule deeply concave, posterior lateral corners rounded but strongly protuberant; eyes completely atrophied. Antennal insertions distant to each other; distance between them about half of head width. Labrum (male, Figs 3, *lb*) with three pairs of spiny protuberances, middle pair less developed, slightly shorter. Left mandible with a single tooth, right with bifid tooth (Fig. 4, *md*). Maxillary palpi (Fig. 4, *mxp1–mpx4*) small, reaching about half of length of head capsule, palpomere 1 minuscule, curved; 2 largest, subglobular, at base pedunculate; 3 subglobular, about half as large as 2; 4 slightly elongated, about 1.15 times as long as wide, roundly pointed distally, with well-defined sensory appendage; all palpomeres simple, lacking sensory processes.

Antennae (male, Fig. 3) about 0.2 mm long, 11-segmented; antennomeres 10 and 11 forming antennal club, 10 subrectangular, 11 conical; scape about as long as wide, about 1.55 times as long as globular pedicel; antennomeres 3–8 transversal, subequal in length, 5 about 1.8 times as wide as long, 7 twice as wide as long; terminal antenomere with dense setae; antenomere 11 with basally originated, long, spatulate, flattened sensilla very weakly-demarcated, almost invisible.

Pronotum (Fig. 6) inversely trapezoidal, elongate, about 1.15 times as long as wide, widest slightly anterior to anterior third, from here evenly convergent pos-

Figs 1–5. *Maeytia macedonica* sp. n: **1.** Dorsal habitus of male; **2.** Dorsal habitus of female; **3.** Head and antennae of male, dorsal view; **4.** Mouthparts of female, ventral view; **5.** Head and antennae of female, dorsal view. Abbreviations: *lb*, labrum; *md*, mandible; *mxp1–4*, maxillary palpi 1–4.

teriad; disc slightly convex; anterior and posterior corners round, anterior and posterior margins straight; lacking sulci and foveae.

Mesoventrite and metaventrite (Fig. 7) separated, mesoventrite subrectangular, with slightly convex anterior margin, shagreened, metaventrite about 1.3 times as long as mesoventrite, meso and metafurca (Fig. 7, *msf*, *mtf*) well-developed; mesoventral process (Fig. 7, *msvp*) short, anterior metaventral process (*amtp*) long, pointed; posterior metaventral process (Fig. 7, *pmtp*) rounded.

Elytra longer than wide, slightly granulate, lacking basal foveae, carinae or striae. Abdomen elongate, more than 4.6 times as long as elytra, first visible tergite (III) shortest, about 1.15 times shorter than 2 (IV) which is about 1.20 times as short than 3 (V); tergites 3 (V) – 6 (VIII) subequal in length, last visible tergite 6 (VIII) roundly pointed; first visible sternite 1 (III) with confluent metacoxal beds (Fig. 8, *mtcb*); paratergites III–VII well-defined.

Legs (Fig. 8) short and robust, mesocoxae confluent, oval and long, as long as one third of combined length of mesoventrite and metaventrite; tibiae strongly enlarged in distal half; metatrochanter simple, lacking spur.

Aedeagus (Fig. 9) elongate, about three times as long as wide sinuose both in lateral and in ventral.

SEXUAL DIMORPHISM. Females (Fig. 5, *lb*) differ from males by having only two pairs of labral spiny protuberances and having antennomere 5 more transverse, twice as wide as long.

NATURAL HISTORY. All four specimens were collected by soil-washing (about 100 kilograms of soil from five nearby situated places with maximal distance about 30 meters) in a non-limestone part of mountains in a valley covered by a deciduous forest dominated by *Carpinus* and *Acer* trees (Figs 13–16).

DISTRIBUTION. North Macedonia (Skopska Crna Gora Mt.)

REMARK. *Mayetia macedonica* is easily separated from its balkanic congeners by lacking sensory appendages on palpomeres, by simple metatrochanter lacking spine and by different structure of aedeagus.

DISCUSSION

The distribution of the west palaeartic *Mayetia* is interesting with all known species, except four balkanic species, distributed exclusively in the western part of the Mediterranean region. The highest number of species is in France, in total 71 species names are recorded from the country, two are shared with Italy and five with Spain, 21 are endemic to Corse. Spain holds 54 species names, two are shared with Portugal. Portugal has 11 and Italy 10 species names. Northern Africa has four species, two species in Algeria and two in Tunisia. Two balkanic species are known from Bosnia and Hercegovina and the Croatian peninsula Istra.

Figs 6–8. *Maeytia macedonica* sp. n: **6.** Pronotum, dorsal view; **7.** Meso and metaventrite; **8.** Metaventricle, abdomen (part), mid and hind legs. Abbreviations: *amtp*, anterior metaventral process; *msf*, mesofurca; *mtcb*, metacoxal beds; *mtf*, metafurca; *msvp*, mesoventral process; *pmtp*, posterior metaventral process.

Fig. 9. *Mayetia macedonica*, aedeagus, ventral view; **Fig. 10.** *Mayetia istriensis*, aedeagus, ventral view (Orousset, 1986: 500, fig. 1); **Fig. 11.** *Mayetia matzenaueri*, aedeagus, ventral view (Orousset, 1986: 500, fig. 2); **Fig. 12.** *Mayetia carpatica*, aedeagus, dorsal view (Decu, 1981: 267, fig. 10); **Figs 13–16.** Collecting sites.

Mayetia istriensis Breit, 1911 (Fig. 10) was described by Breit (1911) according to some specimens collected by him and Curti in nearby Opatija (Abazzia) on Učka Mts. (Mte. Maggiore) in the eastern part of Istrian peninsula by the sifting of deep litter in deciduous forests. *Mayetia matzenaueri* Bernhauer, 1912 (Fig. 11) was described by Bernhauer (1912) according to two specimens collected by Matzenauer in Jablanica, Hercegovina. Both last species were treated by Coiffait (1955) in his revision where the illustrations of some important body parts as well as the aedeagus were provided. Orousset (1987) designated the lectotype and also provided the drawing of the aedeagus for both species. *Mayetia carpatica* (Fig. 12) is the only Carpathic species which was described by Decu (1981) according to the large series of 70 specimens from Southern Carpathians (Mehedenți and Vilcan Mts.). Later a large number, 135 specimens were collected by T. Struyve and G. Makranczy (Struyve 2022) also in Southern Carpathians. This species was so far collected on six different localities.

MATERIAL STUDIED: *Mayetia istriensis*: CROATIA, 2ex, with one label “Dr. v. Beszédes / M. Maggiore / Istrien” [white, printed] (NMPC, PCPH). *Mayetia matzenaueri*: BOSNIA AND HERCEGOVINA: 1♀, with two labels “Jablanica” [white, hand written], “Herzegovina / V. M. Duchon” [white, printed] (NMPC); 1♀, with two labels “Hercegov. / Matzenauer” [white, printed] / “Typus” [red, printed] (NMPC); 1♂, with two labels “Jablanica / Matzenauer” [white, printed], “*Mayetia* / *Matzenaueri* Brh. / Det. Dr. Obenberger” [white, printed and handwritten] (NMPC); 1♀, with two labels “Jablanica / Matzenauer” [white, printed], “*Leptotyphlus* / *perpusillus* Dod. [sic] / Det. Dr. Obenberger” [white, printed and handwritten] (PCPH).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Peter Hlaváč was supported by the Ministry of Culture of the Czech Republic (DKRVO 2024–2028/5. I. a, National Museum, 00023272). Jiří Janák thanks Slavcho Hristovski (Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, Skopje, North Macedonia) for his help in organising the field trips and arranging collecting permits. Our special thanks go to Jean Orousset (Antony, France) for valuable comments to the manuscript as well as for originals of his drawings of the aedeagi of *Mayetia istriensis* Breit, 1911 and *Mayetia matzenaueri* Bernhauer, 1912.

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